

Hazard assessment methodologies applicable to the SSbD framework: where we are

Eleonora Longhin^a, Sivakumar Murugadoss^a, Ann-Karin Olsen^a, Tanima SenGupta^a, Elise Rundén-Pran^a and Maria Dusinska^a

^a *The Climate and Environmental Research Institute NILU*

eml@nilu.no

From its roots in early Safe by Design (SbD) ideas, the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) concept has evolved over the years and through various European projects and activities into the comprehensive framework we know nowadays. In response to growing global environmental concerns, SSbD extended the SbD principles to include sustainability. This led to the European Commission's 2023 formal recommendation on SSbD, which provides structured guidelines and methodologies. The hazard assessment step in this recommendation is based on the classification and categorization system outlined in the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation. The applicability of the EC framework has been tested through case studies. Some challenges have been highlighted, including the presence of data gaps, and cost and effort needed to collect the data, especially in the early development stages of the substances and materials.

Intelligent testing strategies to generate new data are needed, along with a tiered approach of the SSbD framework, increasing the requirements for data and the complexity of the tools along the chemical/material innovation. In this respect, the use of non-animal based new approach methodologies (NAMs) for hazard and risk assessments is envisioned as an important tool for data generation in SSbD. NAMs include *in vitro* and *in silico* methods, and form the backbone of innovative, exposure-led, and hypothesis-driven risk assessments. However, guidelines are still lacking on which methodologies and tools could be used (alone, or/and in combination) in the different stages of the assessment.

Within the new European project ANALYST, the state of the art on hazard and risk assessment methodologies relevant to SSbD was compiled. To do this, a comprehensive literature review was conducted on published literature, grey literature and unpublished research (presented at conferences and workshops). Key methodologies and concepts from recent advancements in SSbD, showcasing innovative tools and strategies for hazard identification, exposure assessment, and risk minimization were scoped. These include probabilistic risk assessment, advanced *in vitro* models, and multi-criteria decision support systems. An overview of methodologies and tools for hazard assessment applied or applicable to the SSbD framework and of the various hazard classes was compiled.

This work will serve as a basis for the implementation of an ANALYST-toolbox, which will consist of methodologies and guidelines for an integrated approach to SSbD, to be operationalized in practice on 3 different cases covering the PVC value chain. In this way, ANALYST will catalyse and empower the industrial sector to achieve the paradigm shift towards chemicals, materials, and products that are inherently safe and sustainable.

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